

Vibrational Processes In Curvilinear Rods Interacting With Viscous Liquid

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Abstract.

The paper the proper and forced steady oscillations of a curvilinear rod interacting with a viscous fluid is considered. On the basis of the principle of possible displacements, solving systems of partial differential equations and corresponding boundary conditions, we form mathematical problem. The problem was solved numerically by the method of orthogonal drift of Godunov and Mueller's method, the natural frequencies of oscillations is founded, and are compared with the results of the experiment.

Keywords: oscillations, viscous fluid, curved rod, orthogonal sweep, possible displacements, natural frequency.

The main component of the main pipeline is a linear part representing a continuous thread welded from separate pipes and laid along the path [1,2]. The linear part of the pipeline is laid in a variety of topographic, geological, hydro-geological and climatic conditions. Along with the areas that have a large bearing capacity, along the route are often sites with soils of low bearing capacity, as well as marshy areas, areas of permafrost soils and others. In addition, main pipelines cross a significant number of natural and man-made obstacles that require appropriate design solutions that ensure both reliable operation of the pipeline. Depending on the terrain, geographic situation at the construction site, and also on technological requirements, the pipeline has curved sections or turns to change its direction. In operation, the curved sections of the pipeline are considered as curvilinear rods in contact with the liquid.

1. Basic relations of linear theory Curved rods

We consider a curvilinear rod formed by the motion of a plane, possibly variable, shape along some flat curve. The axial line of a plane curve, so that the center of mass of the generatrix of the figure always lies on this curve (Fig. 1).

Fig.1, a. The element of a curved rod.

We introduce the curvilinear orthogonal coordinate system (x, y, z) and unit vectors $(\bar{t}, \bar{n}, \bar{b})$, In which are directed respectively along the tangent, normal and binormal to the center line. All the Lamé coefficients are identically equal to one. Using the known rules for differentiating the normal and tangent [1]

$$\frac{d\bar{n}}{dx} = -K\bar{t}, \quad \frac{d\bar{t}}{dx} = -K\bar{n},$$

where K - curvature of the center line. Taking into account that all other derivatives with respect to the coordinates of unit vectors are equal to zero, it is not difficult to find an expression for the displacement vector gradient:

$$\text{grad}\bar{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} - K u_y & \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} + K u_x & \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix},$$

u_x, u_y, u_z - components of the displacement vector. Then the components of the Cauchy strain tensor in the coordinate system (x, y, z) have the form [4]

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{xx} &= \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} - K u_y; \quad \varepsilon_{yy} = \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y}; \quad \varepsilon_{zz} = \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \\ \varepsilon_{yx} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial z} \right]; \quad \varepsilon_{xz} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} \right]; \\ \varepsilon_{xy} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} + K u_x + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In accordance with the hypothesis of flat sections under deformation, the bars normal to the axis of the rod move like a rigid body and remain normal to the deformed center line. We denote by u, v, w components of the displacement vector of the axial line, and through φ, ψ, θ - angles of rotation of the normal section with respect to the axes x, y, z respectively. Then the components of the displacement vector of an arbitrary point of the normal section within the linearity have the form:

$$u_x = u - \theta y - \psi z, \quad u_y = w - \psi z, \quad u_z = v - \psi y \quad (2)$$

Let $\bar{t}^*, \bar{n}^*, \bar{b}^*$ - unit vectors directed respectively along the tangent normal of the binormal to the deformed centerline. In the linear approximation

$$\bar{t}^* = (1, \theta, \psi)^T, \quad \bar{n}^* = (-\theta, 1, \psi)^T \quad (3)$$

Hence, taking into account (1) and relation

$$\bar{t}^* = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(u, v, w)^T + \bar{t} \quad (4)$$

we find the geometric relationship between the movements of the center line and the angles of rotation of the section θ and φ :

$$\theta = (\bar{t}^*, \bar{n}^*) = \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + K u, \quad \psi = (\bar{t}^*, \bar{b}) = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \quad (5)$$

Substituting (3) into (2), we obtain the expressions for the components of the strain tensor of an arbitrary normal cross section:

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - K w - y \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} - z \left[\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} - K \psi \right], \quad \varepsilon_{zz} = \varepsilon_{zy} = \varepsilon_{yy} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Shifts ε_{xy} and ε_{xz} In the framework of the hypothesis of plane cross sections can not be determined, since they essentially depend on the geometric factors of the cross section. Without giving up altogether from the hypothesis of plane sections, we assume that the tangential stresses have the same distribution in the normal cross section, as in the case of prismatic rods for which the relation [2]

$$M = GJ\tau$$

where M - torque relative to the axis of rotation arising in the normal section; τ - the relative angle of twist of the section; G - shear modulus; J - Moment of inertia of the section in torsion. In [5], on the basis of the theory of shells, the last assumption and the formula (6) were proved for a sufficiently small curvature K . For a curved rod, that is nothing less than the torsion of a deformed axial line. In order to carry out the geometrical connection between t and the section rotations, we use the differentiation formula for the Franse-Serre normal [3]:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{n}^*}{\partial x} = -K \bar{t}^* + \tau \bar{b}^* \quad (7)$$

where K^* - curvature of the deformed centerline. Multiplying both sides of (7) scalarly by b^* , we have

$$\tau = \frac{\partial \bar{n}^*}{\partial x} b^* = \frac{\partial \bar{n}^*}{\partial x} \bar{t}^* \bar{n}^*$$

From this, taking (4) into account and performing differentiation, we obtain, up to linear terms

$$\tau = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} - K; & K\theta; & \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \\ 1; & \theta; & \psi \\ -\theta; & 1; & \varphi \end{bmatrix} \approx \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} + K\psi \quad (8)$$

The equations of motion of the rod are derived on the basis of the principle of possible displacements. To do this, you need to determine the complete virtual work of internal and external forces acting on the rod, including inertia forces.

The virtual work of normal stresses can be found from the relations

$$\delta A_n = - \int_S \int_L \sigma_{xx} \delta \varepsilon_{xx} dx dS = - \int_L (T \delta \varepsilon + M_1 \delta x_1 + M_2 \delta x_2) dx \quad (9)$$

where S - area of normal section; L - length of centerline

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - Kw, \quad x_1 = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x}, \quad x_2 = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} - K\psi, \quad (10)$$

$$T = \int_S \sigma_{xx} dS, M_1 = \int_S \sigma_{xx} y dS, M_2 = \int_S z \sigma_{xx} dS$$

with the help of Hooke's law

$$\sigma_{xx} = E \varepsilon_{xx} \quad (11)$$

it is not difficult to integrate relations

$$T = ES\varepsilon, M_1 = E(J_1 x_1 + J_{12} x_2), M_2 = E(J_1 x_1 + J_{21} x_2) \quad (12)$$

Here we introduce moments of inertia

$$J_1 = \int_S y^2 dS, \quad J_2 = \int_S z^2 dS, \quad J_{12} = J_{21} = \int_S yz dS,$$

Cross-sectional area S . Taking into account the assumed assumption about the nature of the distribution of shear stresses, we determine the virtual work of the torque that arises in the cross section

$$\delta A_x = - \int_L M \delta \tau dx \quad (13)$$

The virtual work of inertial forces within the hypothesis of plane sections is reduced to the form

$$\delta A_p = - \int_L \rho \{ (\ddot{u} \delta u + \ddot{w} \delta w + \ddot{v} \delta v) + J_1 \ddot{\theta} \delta \theta + J_2 \ddot{\psi} \delta \psi + I \ddot{\varphi} \delta \varphi \} dx \quad (14)$$

where ρ - the bulk density of the rod, and I is the polar moment of inertia of the normal section with respect to the x axis. Let the vector of external force forces act along the rod $\bar{F} = (F_x F_y F_z)^T$, and at the edge $x = L$, an external force $\bar{G} = (G_x, G_y, G_z)^T$ and the external moment $m = (m_x, m_y, m_z)^T$ with respect to the center of mass of the end of the rod, then the operation of external actions of virtual displacements is described by expression

$$\delta A_t = \int (F_x \delta u + F_y \delta w + F_z \delta v) dx + (G_x \delta u + G_y \delta w + G_z \delta v + m_x \delta \varphi - m_y \delta \psi - m_z \delta \theta) \Big|_{x=L}$$

complete virtual work according to the principle of possible displacements must be zero

$$\delta A_n + \delta A_x + \delta A_p + \delta A_t = 0. \quad (15)$$

Substituting relations (9), (13), and (14) in (15) after the standard integration procedure by parts, we obtain the momentum law

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + KQ_1 - \rho S \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + F_x &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial Q_1}{\partial z} + KT - \rho S \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} - F_y &= 0 \quad (16) \\ \frac{\partial Q_2}{\partial x} + \rho S \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} - F_z &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

at the equation of the law of conservation of angular momentum

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial M}{\partial x} + KM_2 - \rho I \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial t^2} + F_x &= 0 \\ Q_1 = \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial x} - \rho J_1 \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial t^2} & \quad (17) \\ Q_2 = \frac{\partial M_2}{\partial x} - \rho J^2 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} - KM & \end{aligned}$$

At the same time, natural boundary conditions are determined

$$\begin{aligned} x = 0: T = G_x \quad Q_1 = -G_y \quad Q_2 = -G_z \\ x = L: M = m_x \quad M_2 = -m_y \quad M_1 = -m_z \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

The relations (5), (6), (8), (10), (12), (17) and (18) form a closed system of algebraic and differential equations with respect to the vector of unknowns

$$Y = (u, w, v, \varphi, \psi, \theta, \varepsilon, x_1, x_2, \tau, T, Q_1, Q_2, M, M_1, M_2)^T \quad (19)$$

If the cross-section of the rod is symmetric to the normal of the centerline, which is characteristic of Bourdon tubes, then

$$J_{12} = J_{21} = 0$$

And consequently, the defining relations have the form

$$\begin{aligned} \text{a) } M_1 = EJ_1 x_1 \quad \text{б) } M_2 = EJ_2 x_2 \quad (20) \\ T = ES\varepsilon \quad M = GJ\tau \end{aligned}$$

It is not difficult to see that the remaining unknowns also break up into two groups corresponding to two subsystems of equations

$$\begin{aligned} \text{a) } x_1 = \frac{d\theta}{dx} \quad \text{b) } x_2 = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} - K\varphi \\ \theta = \frac{dw}{dx} + Ku \quad \psi = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - Kw$$

$$\tau = \frac{d\varphi}{dx} + K\psi$$

$$Q_1 = \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial x} - \rho J_1 \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial t^2}$$

$$Q_2 = \frac{\partial M_2}{\partial x} - KM - \rho J_2 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial Q_1}{\partial x} - KT + \rho S \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} - F_y = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial Q_2}{\partial x} + \rho S \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} - F_z = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + KQ_1 - \rho S \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + F_x = 0$$

$$\frac{dM}{dx} + KM_2 - \rho I \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial t^2} - F_x = 0$$

The system (20a), (21a) describes a planar flexural-longitudinal motion, the system (20b), (21b) is orthogonal to it flexural-torsional.

When calculating thin-walled rods, the first relation (20a) should be changed to take into account the Karman effect

$$M_1 = E J_1 k \chi_1$$

Where k is the coefficient of stiffness reduction due to transverse deformation of the cross section during bending. This coefficient depends on the shape of the cross section and the curvature K. The calculation technique is given in [4].

Fig. 1, b. Transition to rotated vectors: a) components of the "rotated" vector $\underline{N}$ in the basis $\underline{i}, \underline{j}, \underline{k}$ b) the components of the vector $\underline{N}$ in the basis $\underline{b}, \underline{n}, \underline{t}$

2. Self-oscillations of an elastic curved rod

It is assumed that for the natural vibrations of the elastic rod, all interactions of inelastic origin, including friction, are absent, and the motion obeys the harmonic law

$$\bar{Y}(x, t) = \bar{Y}_0(x) e^{i\omega t} \quad (22)$$

where $\bar{Y}_0(x)$ - vector of proper forms; ω - oscillation frequency. In this case

$$\bar{F} = \bar{G} = \bar{m} = 0, \beta_j = 0 \quad (j=1 \dots 4) \quad (23)$$

Below are examples of calculating the natural vibrations of an elastic rod, performed in accordance with the theory described above, and the results of experimental studies.

Example 1. Oscillations of a solid curved rod. We consider a steel curvilinear rod of constant rectangular section and constant curvature, one end of which is rigidly embedded, and the other is free. Dimensions of the rod (in mm): length 210; Cross-section 3.1 x 18.6; The radius of curvature is 56.8. The small side of the section is parallel to the norm of the center line. Their own flexural-longitudinal oscillations are subject to investigation. Eliminating algebraic constraints from the equations (21, a), after identical transformations and replacing (22), we have a system of ordinary differential equations solved with respect to the derivatives (here and below, the index for unknown eigenmodes is omitted)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{du}{dx} &= \frac{T}{ES} + Kw & \frac{dw}{dx} &= Q_1 - Ku \\ \frac{d\theta}{dx} &= \frac{M_1}{EJ_1 k} & \frac{dT}{dx} &= -KQ_1 - \rho S \omega^2 u \\ \frac{dQ_1}{dx} &= KT + \rho S \omega^2 w & \frac{dM_2}{dx} &= Q_1 - \rho S \omega^2 \theta \end{aligned}$$

where for solid rods $K = 1$.

Table 1. Comparison of theoretical and experimental values of frequencies

Frequency	$\omega/2\pi$ (Гц)		
№ Frequencies	1	2	3
Calculation	75,8	212	713
experiment	75	204	680

By virtue of the fixing conditions on the edges of the rod, the relations

$$\begin{aligned} x = 0, u = w = \theta = 0 \\ x = L, T = Q_2 = M_1 = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

You must also find the values c_0 , under which the system of equations with boundary conditions (2.24) has nonzero solutions, the last problem was solved numerically by the Godunov orthogonal sweep method, found for the values $E = 19.6 \cdot 10^9$ MPa, $\rho = 8 \text{ g/sm}^3$ the first three natural frequencies are shown in Table 1 together with the results of the experiment [6].

According to the table, the difference between the experimental and calculated data is greater for high frequencies, but generally does not exceed 5%.

Example 2. Oscillations of a thin-walled curvilinear rod. We study the own flexural-longitudinal oscillations of the Bourdon steel tube of the flat-oval cross section fixed as well as the rod in example 1. The tube dimensions (in mm): length 240; Wall thickness 0,2; The major and minor axes of section 9.5 and 3.2; The radius of curvature is 45.2. The Young's modulus is $E = 20.6 \cdot 10^4$ MPa; Bulk density $\rho = 7,8 \text{ g/sm}^3$; Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0,25$. The formulation of the spectral problem is given by the relations (3), (4). This time the coefficient of stiffness reduction is equal to 0.129. The minimum natural frequency obtained in solving the boundary value problem by the orthogonal sweep method is 88.6 Hz. According to the experimental data, the first resonance of the tube was observed at 100 Hz. The somewhat understated calculated value of the frequency is explained by the fact that the rod model does not take into account the real conditions of fastening at the ends of the tube, near which the Karman effect manifests itself to a lesser degree.

Example 3. Comparative analysis of the flexural-longitudinal and flexural-torsional oscillations of a curved rod. The equations of the proper flexural-torsional oscillations of an elastic rod are obtained from the relations (20), (21b) as a result of the change of variables (22). In a form adapted to the implementation of the orthogonal drift method, they have the form of a system of first-order differential equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\varphi}{dx} &= \frac{M}{GJ} - K\psi & \frac{d\nu}{dx} &= \psi \\ \frac{d\psi}{dx} &= \frac{M_2}{GJ_2} - K\varphi & \frac{dM}{dx} &= -KM_2 - \rho I \omega^2 \varphi \\ \frac{dQ_2}{dx} &= \rho S \omega^2 w & \frac{dM_2}{dx} &= Q_2 + KM_2 + \rho J_2 \omega^2 \psi \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

A rigidly clamped rod with a free end corresponds to boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} x = 0, \varphi = \psi = \mathcal{G} = 0 ; \\ x = L, M = Q_2 = M_2 = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Table 2 shows the calculated and experimental values of the first two natural frequencies of flexural-torsional oscillations of a straight and two circular pipelines with a fixed liquid fixed in supports. The test

was carried out by the stand [6], designed to study the parametric oscillations of elastic pipelines of aircraft structures [4]. The pipe samples are made of steel 12 x 18N1 OT with an outer diameter of 8 mm, an internal diameter of 7 mm.

Table 2.

Variation of frequency as a function of the angle and length of the rod

Angle of solution	Length (mm)	1 Frequency (Hz)		2 Frequency (Hz)	
		calculation	experiment	calculation	experiment
0°	800	64,2	61,2	177	166
90°	765	64,7	64,1	185	170
180°	625	84,0	61,5	243	170

The density of the pipe material is 7.9 g / cm³ elastic modulus E= 18,0*10⁴ MPa [5], Poisson's ratio ν=0,3 AMG-10 oil with a density of 0.85 g / cm (GOST 6794 - 75) was used as a working fluid. In this case, the reduced density of the tube, taking into account the mass of the liquid, is 9.5 g / cm³.

According to Table 6, the calculated data are in better agreement with experiment with less curvature of the tube, but in the latter case, with the reference to [6], it is possible that the fastening can be loosened. The solutions of the boundary value problems (22), (23), (24), (25) were numerically studied in terms of the curvature parameter of the axis by the example of oscillations of a rod with the following dimensionless geometric relations

$$\frac{SL}{KJ_1} = 7238; \frac{SL}{J_2} = 1505; \frac{SL^2}{I} = 1246; \frac{EJ^2_2}{GL} = 3.865$$

For each type of vibration: flexural-longitudinal and flexural-torsion, in tables 3 and 4, respectively, the values of the first five natural frequencies c₀ depending on the value of KL, characterizing the degree of curvature of the axial line. The calculation was carried out without taking into account the inertia of the section rotation. The unit of time is considered equal L(p/E)^{1/2}.

Table 3.

Variation in frequency as a function of the parameter characterizing the degree of curvature of the axial line (flexural-longitudinal oscillations)

N	KL	Eigen values				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	0	0,04133	0,2590	0,7252	1,421	1,571
2	0,78	0,04184	0,2425	0,7043	1,383	1,737
3	1,57	0,04345	0,2091	0,6582	1,334	2,044
4	3,14	0,05046	0,1593	0,5433	1,207	2,090
5	4,71	0,06453	0,1413	0,4240	1,043	1,910
6	6,28	0,08920	0,1463	0,3237	1,8656	1,684

Example 4. Oscillations of a rod with a load at the end. Let one end of the rod, as before, be sealed, and at the free end the cargo is rigidly fixed, which we will consider undeformable. We will show how the inertia of the cargo in the boundary conditions is taken into account. According to [7], the kinetic energy of a solid is given by

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int (\bar{V} + \bar{\Omega} \bar{r})^2 \rho \bar{r} dU \quad ,$$

Where the integration is performed over the entire volume of the body U of the density p_r;

Ω - angular velocity; V, r - the velocity of an arbitrary reference point, rigidly connected with the body, and the radius vector from this point to the center of mass. Expanding the brackets in (7) and performing the integration, we obtain

Table 4.

The change in frequency as a function of the parameter characterizing the degree of curvature of the axial line (flexural-torsional oscillations)

N	KL	Eigen values				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	0	0,09063	0,5680	1,590	3,117	5,153
2	0,78	0,07472	0,3827	1,319	2,822	4,843
3	1,57	0,06633	0,2809	0,9891	2,362	4,305
4	3,14	0,07672	0,2240	0,7271	1,896	3,680
5	4,71	0,1045	0,2026	0,5272	1,485	3,066

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \mu \bar{V}^2 + \mu \bar{r}_0 \bar{V} \bar{\Omega} + \frac{1}{2} \bar{\Omega} J \bar{\Omega} \quad (27)$$

where $\mu = \int \rho_r dU$ - load weight; $\bar{r}_0 = \frac{1}{\mu} \int \bar{r} p_r dU$ - radius-vector from the point of reference to the center of mass; J is the load inertia tensor at the reference point. As a point of reference, let us take the point of the axial line $x = L$. Then, taking into account the conditions for securing the load, also the notation for the positive section rotations in Fig. 1, we can write the coordinates of the vectors V and Ω in the basis $(\bar{t}, \bar{n}, \bar{b})$:

$$X=L; \quad \bar{V} = \frac{d}{dt} (u, w, v)^T; \quad \bar{\Omega} = \frac{d}{dt} (\varphi - \psi, \theta)^T \quad (28)$$

Vector components r_c and the tensor J in the same coordinate system we denote by

$$\bar{r}_c = (x_c, y_c, z_c)^T; \quad J = \{J_{ij}\}; \quad (i, j = x, y, z) \quad (29)$$

With allowance for (28), (29), the coordinate representation of the kinetic energy (27) has the form

$$T = \mu \left(\frac{1}{2} (u^2 + w^2 + v^2) + y_0 (\dot{v} \dot{\varphi} - \dot{u} \dot{\theta}) + x_0 (\dot{w} \dot{\theta} - \dot{v} \dot{\psi}) + \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{2} (J_{yy} \dot{\psi}^2 + J_{zz} \dot{\theta}^2 + J_{xy} \dot{\varphi}^2 - J_{yz} \dot{\psi} \dot{\theta} - J_{yz} \dot{\psi} \dot{\varphi} + J_{yz} \dot{\theta} \dot{\varphi}) \right)$$

Hence, neglecting the time variation of the vector $\bar{r}_0$ and the tensor J at small amplitudes of motion, and, calculating in the linear approximation with the help of the d'Alembert principle, the virtual work of the inertia forces acting on the load, we obtain the natural conditions for oscillations of the rod at the edge $x=L$:

$$Q_1 = \mu (\ddot{W} + x_0 \ddot{\theta} - z_0 \ddot{\varphi}),$$

$$Q_1 = \mu (\ddot{v} + x_0 \ddot{\psi} - z_0 \ddot{\varphi})$$

$$T = \mu (-\ddot{u} + z_0 \ddot{\psi} - y_0 \ddot{\theta}) \quad (30)$$

$$M_1 = -\mu (x_0 \ddot{W} + y \ddot{u}) - J_{zz} \ddot{\theta} - J_{zx} \ddot{\varphi} + J_{zy} \ddot{\psi}$$

$$M_2 = -\mu (x_0 \ddot{v} - z_0 \ddot{W}) - J_{zz} \ddot{\theta} - J_{zx} \ddot{\varphi} + J_{zy} \ddot{\psi}$$

It follows from conditions (30) that the center of mass of the cargo does not lie in the plane of the center line, or the centrifugal moments of inertia J_{zx} , J_{zy} . The flexural-torsional and flexural-longitudinal oscillations are interconnected even if the corresponding unknowns in equations (20), (21) are separated. Consider a rod with the parameters specified in Example 3. ($KL = 3.14$), and assume that the load is fixed symmetrically with respect to the plane of the center line. Then

$$z_0 = J_{zx} = J_{zy} = 0 \quad ,$$

And flexural-longitudinal oscillations do not depend on flexural-torsional oscillations. In the case of natural oscillations, conditions (30) after the replacement of (1) are transformed to the form

$$T = \mu\omega^2(u + y_0\theta),$$

$$Q_1 = \mu\omega^2(-W - x_0\theta),$$

$$M_1 = \mu\omega^2(x_0W - y_0u) + J_{zz}\omega^2\theta,$$

$$M = \omega^2(\mu y_0v + J_{xx}\varphi + J_{xy}\psi),$$

$$Q_2 = \mu\omega^2(-v - x_0\psi - y_0\varphi)$$

$$M_2 = \omega^2(\mu x_0v + J_{yy}\psi - J_{yz}\varphi)$$

Let the cargo be made in the form of a rigid homogeneous beam with a length of 0.3L, and $y_0=0$. For the above parameters of the rod and load, the first five eigenvalues of the boundary value problem (23), (24), (30), found by the orthogonal sweep method, are given in Table 5, depending on the mass of the cargo.

Table 5.

The eigenfrequencies of the rod as a function of body weight.

m	Eigen values				
0	0,05044	0,1591	0,5419	1,198	2,064
0,1	0,04207	0,1161	0,3500	0,8259	1,499
0,5	0,02770	0,07410	0,2838	0,7400	1,386
1	0,02110	0,05784	0,2612	0,6969	1,312

Figures 2a, b, c show the graphs of the eigenforms w , U and the oscillations of the rod with a mass twice that of the weight of the load, respectively, at the first, second, and third natural frequencies. According to the calculation results, the presence of a load at the end of the rod leads to a rod of natural oscillation frequencies, no significant qualitative changes were observed.

3. The intrinsic oscillations of a curved rod contacting a viscous liquid.

The formulation of the eigenvalue problem in the presence of viscous friction formally coincides with the formulation of the problem considered above for an elastic rod. By natural vibrations of a viscoelastic rod, we mean solutions of a homogeneous boundary value problem for a system of equations (21) of the form (22), where, in contrast to the elastic case, the natural frequency ω and own form $\bar{Y}$ oscillations can take complex values. The real and imaginary parts of the quantity have a physical meaning, respectively, the frequency and the rate of decay of the oscillatory process in time. The logarithmic damping decrement is calculated from formula

$$\delta = 2\pi \frac{|\text{Im } \omega|}{\text{Re } \omega}.$$

Using the replacement (22), the eigenvibration problem reduces to the spectral problem for a system of ordinary differential equations in the parameter ω . In the case of a plane-parallel motion, this system has the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{du}{dx} &= \frac{T}{ES(1 + \beta_3\omega i)} + Kw, & \frac{dw}{dx} &= \theta - Ku, \\ \frac{d\theta}{dx} &= \frac{M_1}{EJ_1k(1 + \beta_1\omega i)}, & \frac{dT}{dx} &= -KQ_1 + u(a_1\omega i - \rho S\omega^2) \\ \frac{dQ_1}{dx} &= KT - w(a_2\omega i - \rho S\omega^2), & \frac{dM_1}{dx} &= Q_1 - \rho J_1\omega^2\theta \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

The boundary value problem (31) was solved numerically by the orthogonal sweep method in complex arithmetic.

Fig.2. Graphs of own forms w, U and vibrations of the rod with mass

A numerical analysis of the problem of the eigenvibrations of a curvilinear rod in contact with a viscous liquid allows one to make.

4. Steady oscillations of the rod.

We propose that the rod is exposed, so that its end at the fixing point makes a plane motion according to a known harmonic law

$$u = U e^{i\omega x}, w = W e^{i\omega x}, \theta_1 = H e^{i\omega x} \quad (32)$$

or taking into account the replacement

$$x = 0: U^0 = U, W^0 = W, \theta_1^0 = H \quad (33)$$

Then the forms of steady-state oscillations are solutions of the boundary-value problems (31), (32), (33). In this case the quantity ω assumes known real values and has the meaning of the circular frequency of the driving force. From physical considerations it is clear that in the presence of dissipation the homogeneous spectral problem (31) will have zero solutions only for complex eigenvalues ω . Consequently, with the Fredholm alternative from the theory of linear differential equations [3] for real values ω the corresponding inhomogeneous boundary value problem (21) always has a unique solution.

This solution, like the solution of the eigenvalue problem, was determined

Using the program tool of the orthogonal sweep method.

In Fig. 3 and 4 (curve 1), the amplitude-frequency characteristics of displacements $v^0(L), W^0(L)$ the free end of the rod with friction parameters, the curvature parameter for a load of the form

$$U = 1, W = H = 0 \quad (34)$$

Fig. 3. Amplitude-frequency characteristics of displacement

Curve 2 in Fig. 3 illustrates the amplitude-frequency characteristic of the displacement $W^0(L)$ when exposed

$$U = H = 0, \quad W = 1. \quad (35)$$

Fig. 4 shows that not always the smallest decrement of oscillations found in solving the spectral problem corresponds to the maximum value of the resonant peak of the forced oscillations. Thus, complex eigenvalues characterize the dissipative characteristics of the structure as a whole. For the analysis of resonant modes, it is necessary to take into account the specific type of external influence. Values of vibration modes U_0 at a point on the frequency $\omega = 0.0504$, close to resonant $U_1 = -1,76 + 24,4i$ и $U_2 = 0,078 - 3,65i$ respectively, in cases of excitation of oscillations (34), (35).

As a result, for a given axial perturbation, it was possible to select such an effect in the orthogonal direction that the amplitude of the longitudinal vibrations of the rod at the first resonance decreased by a factor of 20. The described effect of vibration damping is caused by the interrelation of transverse and longitudinal oscillations and is in principle impossible in the case of a straight rod.

Fig. 4. Amplitude-frequency characteristics of displacement

Figure 5 shows the calculation scheme of one of the problems considered in the work, in Fig. 6 and 7 - supercritical behavior of the rod.

Fig.5. The calculation scheme of the problem

Fig.6. Cross-sectional bending of the rod

Fig.7. Supercritical behavior of the rod for longitudinally transverse bending

An analytical construction of the tangent stiffness matrix of a finite element of a geometrically nonlinear Bernoulli-Euler stem is performed. Unlike most papers devoted to geometrically nonlinear rods, in this paper the rod is considered in accordance with the Bernoulli-Euler hypothesis.

Conclusions.

1. With increasing intrinsic motion, the damping decrements increase with internal friction and decrease with external friction. Moreover, with an increase in intense dissipation, aperiodic regimes (purely imaginary eigenvalues) arise, beginning with the highest numbers of proper motion, in the case of internal friction, and from the lowest numbers of proper motions, in the case of external friction.

Exceptions to this rule were observed only for inhomogeneous external friction for strongly curved rods ($KL > 3.14$), for which the maximum damping decrement with KL increases from the first proper motion to the second one. In the case of a straight rod, a similar effect was first established by V. Biderman [8].

2. For homogeneous dissipation, the eigenforms coincide with the corresponding eigenmodes of the elastic vibrations corresponding to the number. In the case of internal friction for vibrational modes, the imaginary parts of the eigenvalues linearly depend on the parameter. In the case of external friction, the imaginary part of the various eigenvalues is the same, does not depend on the curvature of the axis, and is determined by expression:

$$\text{Im } \omega = \frac{J_1 k}{2SL^2} \tilde{a}_2$$

3. If the friction is inhomogeneous, the eigenmodes depend on the intensity of the dissipation, and the oscillations of the various spatial points are shifted in phase. Owing to the allowance for energy dissipation, the viscoelastic rod model makes it possible to investigate stimulated steady-state oscillations at resonances.

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